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NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Thirteenth meeting of the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) Steering Group, 10:30 am, Tuesday 27th November 2001, British Geological Survey, Natural History Museum, London.

AGENDA

1. Apologies
2. Report of the twelfth meeting of the Group
3. Matters arising from the report of the twelfth meeting
4. BADC progress report covering the last 6 months
5. Verbal feedback on NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
6. NERC metadata gateway
7. Budget
8. Any other business
9. Date of next meeting

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BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 2. Report of the twelfth meeting of the BADC Steering Committee.

The report of the twelfth meeting of the BADC Steering Committee is attached. The Committee is asked to approve the report.

Agenda Item 3. Matters arising from the report of the twelfth meeting.

Actions continued from the report of the eleventh meeting were:

1. **N. Collins** to investigate possible BADC representation on the ad hoc NERC/Met Office Joint Panel on Aircraft Operation.
2. **N. Collins** to investigate possible BADC representation in thematic programmes steering committees and allocation of part of the programmes budget to data custody.
3. **N. Collins** to investigate the setting up of a formal mechanism to make BADC aware of all potential data coming out of NERC funded atmospheric research.
4. **N. Collins** to explore the possibility of implementing a new funding scheme.
5. **B. Lawrence** to write to Bob Gurney (Reading) about how to deal with ocean data.

Actions in the report of the last meeting were:

6. **B. Lawrence** to provide N. Collins with letter highlighting possible funding difficulties.
7. **B. Lawrence** to request funding for the NERC metadata gateway at the review.

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BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Minutes of the twelfth meeting of the BADC Steering Committee, held at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory on the Friday the 19th of January 2001. Meeting start time: 10:30 am.

Present:

Dr P. Valdes, chair	(PV)	Reading
Mr N. Collins	(NC)	NERC
Dr T. Cox	(TC)	Cambridge
Dr C. Hall	(CH)	UKMO
Dr B. Lawrence	(BL)	BADC
Dr D. Marbouty	(DM)	ECMWF
Dr S. Pepler	(SP)	BADC
Dr C. Reeves	(CR)	UEA
Dr G. Vaughan	(GV)	Aberystwyth
Dr B. Whitaker	(BW)	Leeds

J. Gondaleker, Secretary, RAL.

1. Apologies

Pr K.R. Browning (Reading), Dr G. Vaughan (Aberystwyth),
Dr H. Bottger (ECMWF, Dr Marbouty attending on his behalf)

2. Report of the eleventh meeting

The committee confirmed the minutes from the 11th meeting.

3. Matters Arising.

Response to action items:

1. BADC representation on the ad hoc NERC/Met Office Joint Panel on Aircraft Operation. Objective not achieved yet. [Action 1: NC — continues.]
2. BADC representation in thematic programmes steering committees and allocation of part of the thematic programmes budget to data custody. Objective not achieved yet. [Action 2: NC — continues.]
3. SPARC liaison and collaboration.

The BADC provided information to aid the SPARC application for further funds. Liaison will be ongoing as necessary (data center liaison now a specific work package in BADC management plan).

4. Action items on BL with respect to modifications to the 5 year plan were all carried out except for action item 2 (page 3) which was not feasible at the time. Some statistics were however provided by Anabelle Menochet as part of her presentation later in the meeting. It was pointed out that a number of potential NERC thematic programmes are approved in principle but "frozen" pending board decisions as to when they should start.
5. A formal mechanism needs to be set up to make the BADC aware of all potential data coming out of NERC funded atmospheric research. Objective not achieved yet. [**Action 3: NC – continues**]
6. Explore the possibilities of implementing new funding schemes. Objective not achieved yet. [**Action 4: NC – continues**]
7. Letters about ocean data to review panel, DC review groups, and Bob Gurney (Reading) about EO Data. [**Action 5: BL; still need to contact Bob Gurney**]
8. Get in touch with DARC about a possible representation on BADC SC. At this stage the BADC is not yet represented, although BL will possibly become a PI.

3. BADC Progress Report

Corrections to the usage statistic data originally provided in the materials to the committee were provided. Financial information was also provided.

BL and SP took the panel through the report concentrating on the highlights. [Not all discussion expanding on material presented was minuted as the secretary was not familiar enough with the details and had not been provided with copies of all the relevant paperwork].

It is now known that the BADC had 700 active users during the years 2000.

The situation with respect to NERC thematic programme funding remains difficult: there is no sign of CWVC approaching the BADC to discuss their requirements under the data management plan (although BL was invited to their kick off meeting, and presented a talk on the responsibilities with respect to the data management plan).

COAPEC data funding has been agreed.

It is hoped that as the Met Office transistions to Exeter it will be possible to find a more efficient data transfer method for the NWP data than the current tape based method. However it was appreciated that the Met Office will be fully stretched achieving the move without worrying about difficulties at the BADC. Nonetheless, the BADC should be invited to a users meeting to discuss the effects of the move and requirements sometime in the next few months.

The beowulf cluster strategy was presented: early use for Myles Allen's Climate Prediction project, followed by BADC research use, and then use by the BADC users as tools for processing NWP (and other) data were provided under the aegis of the expected funding. The requirement for the extra processing needed soon was stressed: based on an

extrapolation from the UKMO Assimilated data product, one would expect every MB of the UKMO NWP product to be downloaded approximately 20 times in one year, which would lead to a delivery of 23 Terabytes a year to users.

(In 2000, the BADC finished with an archive of 1.3 Terabytes of data. 0.47 Terabytes were delivered to users. The UKMO Assimilated product consisted of 0.05 Terabytes, but users requested 0.105 Terabytes of this data. Extrapolations to the end of next year would have a BADC archive of 12 Terabytes and user downloads as high as 23 Terabytes in the year).

The BADC finances were reported as consistent with predictions, although BL highlighted his concern that without additional funding next year there would be no contingency available (even if staff were frozen), and that things could become difficult as users downloaded data rather than processed data (which would be necessary because there would not be the staff resource to provide them with processed data).

NC suggested BL provide a letter highlighting possible funding difficulties to him by early February. [Action 6: BL]

The Steering Committee were advised and approved the plan to hire Mr Sam Dean for a year contract using the funding released between Dr Gray being funded elsewhere and the acquisition of a new research assistant to BL.

A new user support person has been appointed from an unusually well qualified short list for the new post.

It was noted by CR that the EXPORT campaign listed as UTLS work (WP08) should in fact be included in the atmospheric chemistry support section (CWP05).

The committee approved the report.

4. The BADC Review

The steering committee was pleased with the good report from the BADC review, but were disappointed the panel had not been able to recommend an excellent grade. The consensus of the steering committee was that the "very good" grade was harsh. The chairman commended present and past BADC staff for their work.

The steering committee specifically disagreed with the weaknesses highlighted by the review:

- CR pointed out that the publicity requirement was not borne out by the steady increase in user statistics. BL commented he thought that the capacity for BADC expansion amongst postgraduate and junior postdoc community must be near saturation. TC commented that the "glossy brochure" mentality prevalent now does not contribute to better science. BL suggested that in order to satisfy this requirement the BADC would need to better target more senior members of the academic community to make them aware of the services the BADC provide (even if they are not likely to become active BADC users).

- A number of members of the steering committee thought that the failure of the BADC to find funding to do more data archaeology was not a reasonable reason to castigate the BADC in this area, particularly given the history: NC pointed out that the BADC as created from the GDF 5 years ago began with half the funding previously provided. Much had been achieved with limited resources.

The steering committee was pleased the panel had recommended the full funding. It was hoped that the NERC data centre review would support that recommendation. NC stated that the BADC had confirmed funding for the next five years of 458K.

The requirement to do more publicity was thought to be unreasonable by the steering committee (as noted above). The requirement to do more data archaeology should be tempered with the knowledge that data archaeology is expensive, labour intensive, and that community input on what data sets are important is essential.

BL advised that he had written to Prof Browning with respect to UWERN data archaeology and as a consequence arrangements were being made to acquire Chilbolton radar data.

The steering committee went through the issues arising one-by-one.

1. Funding issues are an ongoing problem.
2. As had been highlighted earlier, the Met Office will be changing it's systems soon. It is to be hoped that the IBM bottleneck will be removed in the process.
5. Links with the JIF programmer are underway.
8. TC pointed out that it would be important to be careful about mixing research and data jobs: young staff might not have the maturity to manage both. BL explained that he planned to attempt to keep staff interested by making sure they were responsible for the data interests of specific large programmes. Motivation through responsibility was thought to be a key.
10. The BADC is currently investigating ways to improve their management information. A new system is planned for the financial year.
12. BL reported that he hoped that CAST would improve things in this area.
13. There was some discussion about the apparent contradiction between the review panels recommendations on publicity: in section 3.2 item 2. the review stated "publicity should be restricted to the UK community ..." and in issue number 13 they stated "the centre could be better advertised, particularly in the UK but also to overseas researchers".
19. BL expressed his disappointment that the review panel had not supported the preprint archive as a number of users had been very positive about this idea. BW pointed out that such archives had not worked in the chemistry community primarily because some journals considered internet publication as "prior publication" thus precluding their inclusion. It was agreed that the inclusion of poster papers and student theses was popular with the users, and probably more important in the long run.

6. The NERC Metadata gateway.

It was noted that the BADC has inherited the maintenance of this gateway (which does not cover all the NERC DDCs).

It was agreed that funding should be sought to support the gateway. BL reported that he planned to make this point to the NERC data centre review. **[Action 7: BL to request funding for this service at the review]**

BW pointed out that it would be important in the future to make sure that such metadata gateways were visible to the internet search engines of the future which would be metadata aware. BL pointed out that the BADC would seek GRID based funding with precisely this in mind: metadata must soon be “machine understandable” as well as “machine readable”.

7. Overview of current topical matters by BADC staff

The meeting then moved to the RAL SSTD visitor’s centre where there were six short presentations via the web:

- Sam Pepler and Chris Harrold: CAST
- Andrew Harwood: GRID
- Anabelle Menochet: BADC Helpdesk and Met Office Data
- Kevin Marsh: UTLS and the Unified Model
- Anne De Rudder: URGENT
- Bryan Lawrence: Future BADC Load and Sam Dean Research.

No minutes were taken during the presentations.

8. AOB

There was no AOB.

9. Date of Next meeting

Not established.

Meeting closed for lunch at 1pm.

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Agenda Item 4. BADC Progress Report.

The progress report of the BADC team covering the last 6 months is enclosed. The Steering Committee is asked to approve the report.

**The British Atmospheric Data Centre
Progress Report (February 2001 - October 2001)**

October 2001

Summary

Workpackage	Issues
CWP01 Met. Data	Users very happy with MIDAS request service, but still need a long-term solution.
CWP02 NWP	UM and ECMWF data continue to be updated. The ERA40 reanalysis is already being extracted.
CWP03 Support	Users continue to get an excellent service. This is an unprompted response from a user - "the BADC is the best place to do business with as far as response time and friendliness".
CWP04 Infrastructure	Considerable effort has gone into ramping up for e-science. The BADC is taking an active part in setting the requirements of e-science. The most immediate impact will be moving to a different storage infrastructure, probably SRB.
CWP05 Programmes CWP06 CAST and services	(Note name change, to show where the emphasis on work is) Registration of CAST and the BADC now integrated.
CWP07 Archaeology	SOUSY radar data negotiations opened.
CWP08 Liaison	The BADC was represented at numerous meetings. Is this the best way to reach our user community?
CWP09 Research	Martin Jukes has joined the BADC. Good progress with clouds.
CWP10 Gateway Main'	Production Gateway now functioning on BADC server.
WP10a Metadata Gateway	No progress due to lack of staff. Richard Stamper starting Dec 1st.
WP11 UTLS	Plans to feed the UM data into the trajectory service
WP12 URGENT	Good progress on acquiring data and data management plans.
WP13 COAPEC	Data extracted and released to COAPEC community.
WP14 DARC	No money for the BADC.
WP15 Data Assimilation	Envisat Data download data using the RAL ATSR groups DDS receiver planned.
WP17 CWVC	A data management plan has been produced, but funds for the archive phase of the programme are not yet known.
WP18 UWRN	(UFAM and FAAM): A meeting with FAAM staff was held at RAL. Discussions underway with Alan Blythe.

1. CWP01: Acquisition of synoptic observational meteorological data.

1.1 MIDAS Land surface station data

This data set consists of daily and hourly surface weather observations from the Met Office station network, extracted from the MIDAS database. Since the change in the MIDAS data structure and underlying database, the normal extraction procedures have been halted. Data formats, units and stations identities have also been changed, yielding inconsistency between the Oracle MIDAS data and the MIDAS Land surface station data currently archived at the BADC. To solve this problem, MIDAS replication at the BADC is being investigated.

In the meantime, a "special request data service" has been put in place to satisfy the demand from BADC users. Data is extracted from the Oracle MIDAS upon requests. This service appears to be highly successful as data extracted corresponds to the exact need of individual users (e.g. parameters for specific station and specific time period), however it is very labour intensive and costly, hence the need to replicate MIDAS at the BADC.

1.2 MetDB Global Radiosonde data

Global Radiosonde data from the Met Office MetDB continue to be updated automatically.

1.3 Global synoptic data:

Some specific synoptic data reports have already been successfully retrieved from the MetDB upon a special user request for the JET2000 campaign. However few problems with extracting global synoptic data have hampered the launch of a new archive of worldwide synoptic data at the BADC. The problems are now being addressed.

1.4 Assimilated data

Global stratospheric analyses for the UARS period (1991- the present) are automatically updated daily from the Met Office. Monthly mean data files are also uploaded on a regular basis.

1.5 Hadley centre data

The GISST, GICE, MOHSST6, MOHMAT4N, Central England Temperature and HADRT data from the Met Office have been updated every month during the year. Northern Hemisphere Geopotential height data from 1998 to present is now also archived and updated monthly at the BADC.

1.6 NCDC CARDS Data for GUAN stations.

CARDS data for 150 stations in the GCOS Upper Air Network (GUAN) have been transferred from NCDC. The data consists of worldwide radiosonde daily ascents from the late 1940s to 1999. This dataset is public and will be made available from the BADC web site shortly.

2. CWP02: Acquisition of NWP data from the UKMO and the ECMWF

2.1 ECMWF Operational

The operational archive is automatically updated on a daily basis and consists of 1.125° and 2.5° gridded upper air data on model and pressure levels. Surface data (both analyses and forecasts) is stored on both grid types as well as the N80 Gaussian grid. The BADC has also responded to occasional requests for data not stored in the archive by extracting subsets of the operational archive from the ECMWF Meteorological Archive and Retrieval System (MARS). Programmes are now routinely run to check for any gaps in the operational data archive resulting in less user queries relating to missing data. The documentation describing

the operational ECMWF data sets held at the BADC has been updated to include: a list of available parameters for each grid type and level type, a description of the grid types and a description of the vertical resolution (level types) in the data archive.

2.2 Near real-time retrieval of ECMWF data

A formal process for requesting ECMWF data in near real-time (NRT) has been created by the BADC to provide researchers with NRT data for specific campaigns. In June 2001, the BADC extracted data for an ocean-modelling project organised by the Southampton Oceanography Centre (SOC). Analysis and forecast data was extracted from the ECMWF archive and processed at the BADC to create subsets in another file format. The new forecast files were then e-mailed to the RRS Discovery where they were used as initial conditions for a model. The provision of data from the BADC allowed comparison of measurements with modelled data during real-time forecasting of biological and physical ocean dynamics at the Iceland-Faeroes Front.

2.3 Re-analysis Data: ERA-15 and ERA-40

Regarding the ERA-15 data set, the BADC has updated the documentation describing the data sets to include details of the available parameters, grid types and level types. The data set remains a valuable climate resource accessed by many users.

Much preparatory work has been undertaken regarding the ERA-40 Re-analysis project. The BADC has consulted widely to examine the most appropriate methods of delivering the data to the research community. A questionnaire was sent out to 450 users and from the 60 responses (and liaison with personnel at the University of Reading) a Provisional Storage Plan was produced for ERA-40 data. The BADC will develop a web-interface to allow users to produce diagnostics, subsets, file conversions and displays of the data. In July 2001, the BADC began extracting ERA-40 data from the MARS archive but due to problems with the observation processing the data produced has not been validated. In October 2001, the ECMWF re-started the model and the BADC continues to extract the data. The running of the model and the extraction are likely to continue until 2003. The BADC will extract the data as it is produced whilst developing the software tools to examine the data. A licensing agreement has been established to allow the BADC to distribute the ERA-40 data to users in a similar manner to the other ECMWF data sets held in its archive. Recent events suggest that such distribution may be possible to specific groups of users worldwide.

2.4 Unified Model

Data from the UM model data has routinely extracted since October 2000. The data arrive on tape at the BADC every 5 days; the global and mesoscale files for each day are around 10 GB in size. These are processed using BADC software to extract the analysis fields, as well as a limited number of forecast fields. These are stored on the BADC archive (with associated web pages and documentation), and are available to registered users. A number of software utilities have also been made available to allow users to access and examine these data.

Scripts have also been obtained to allow the BADC to extract historical UM data from the Met Office, which will allow us to extend the data archive further back in time.

3. CWP03: User Support

The BADC provides support to its users by both e-mail and telephone. A total of 639 significant user queries have been serviced during the period October 2000 to October 2001. Some queries can require a substantial amount of effort - for example a request for a specific piece of data to be extracted from the Met Office archives or maintenance of Data Ordering Service.

Better documentation has significantly reduced the number of queries in areas such as file formats, data documentation and file transfer. Unfortunately 40% of queries regard data availability. This can be attributed to the problems with the MIDAS surface station data.

The current rate of new user registration is 1.5 per working day. The number of user registrations varies during the year, peaking in March and in the summer months. The total number of registered users with access to restricted datasets is 1686.

4. CWP04: System Infrastructure

4.1 Storage plans

We are currently developing our plans for data storage with a view to the e-science/Grid world of the future. As part of this we plan to use the Storage Resource Broker (SRB) produced by the San Diego Super Computer Centre. The SRB is a middleware product that provides a uniform interface for connecting to data resources over a network. It is recommended and supported by the DTI Core Programme for e-Science. This would constitute a radical departure from the current filesystem storage method.

In order to scope the amount of data storage needed for the next few years a data volume plan has been produced. The main datasets are ECMWF ERA40, Envisat and UM. Cloud data will also be significant. The expected storage required by the end of 2002 is approximately 20TB. This has prompted the acquisition of a new tape library and additional disks.

4.2 Web

Results of a web survey conducted in July 2001 have highlighted problems with the current BADC website. Despite 63% of user replies have rated the BADC web site as very good (and 16% rated the site as outstanding), orientation in the BADC web site appeared to be an issue for most users. To address the problem efficiently, a new BADC web site is currently being re-designed and will be launched in the New Year.

4.3 Registration

The user registration system has continued to be improved during this year. The improvements make it easier for users, reduce the workload on the BADC team members and reduce the possibility of errors being made.

The registration system has been divided into two distinct steps: user registration and application for access to datasets. User registration involves the user submitting their personal details via a form on our web site. The details are stored in our database and an account is set up for them automatically. Users then request access to the datasets they require. Previously this would always have required them to post a signed agreement form to us. This is still the case where a signed agreement is required (for example, for access to UKMO data). However, in many cases the application can now be processed electronically. Where there is an external authoriser for a dataset, such as the PI, they are automatically e-mailed details of the request. When the BADC receives approval the user will be granted access to the datasets. External authorisers now have access to a web interface which allows them to view details of all users who have registered for access to their dataset.

The BADC web site now also allows users to update their personal details and to change their account password. This helps in keeping our user database up to date and reduces the number of queries to our helpdesk about forgotten passwords.

The registration process now leaves a permanent cookie on the users machine, which gives us greater ability to monitor the usage of the BADC web site.

During user registration the user is now asked if they want to be part of our 'collaboration initiatives' that have been set up under the CAST project. See the CAST section for more details.

4.4 E-Science

The advent of e-science would appear to indicate that the UK is about to enter a period of rapid evolution of sophistication of the internet-based tools that will become available for doing science. These tools will range from better, more efficient, algorithms for network transport, via smart methods of handling data archives and making the best use of computer resources, to sophisticated methods of handling the knowledge inherent in computerised data. These last tools are very likely to be based on ideas and software development that have occurred in the context of research into Artificial Intelligence.

As is often the case when it has been suggested that software and computers will take over, much of the hype about e-science is overstated. However, it is very clear that there is a large amount of money floating around, and that e-science will influence the evolution of the BADC. Accordingly we have invested a considerable amount of time on e-science this year, particularly Lawrence's time. There have been four components to our work on e-science:

- Understanding what it all means,
- Assessing the implications of e-science on how we will do things in the future,
- Liasing with EU DataGrid (to be explained below), and
- Taking part and leading in the development of proposals for e-science funding.

Assessing what it all means has involved attending a large number of meetings and reading a lot! The BADC was fortunate to obtain a modicum of funding from the CLRC to help with this. In the process of the internal work on e-science, we have represented the NERC community to a wider audience at meetings involving cross-council activities. Most of the presentations, and many summary documents produced during the year are available on the CAST e-science web pages (and while the pages are restricted, BADC steering committee members are welcome to register and look at the material produced).

Regardless of our success in e-science bids, it is obvious that the impact of e-science technologies will be considerable: we are already getting considerable pressure from the user community to install e-science tools: in particular, the Live Access Server). We are also noting that many of the community are choosing to use the US National [] website to diagnose NCEP data, in preference to using ECMWF data from the BADC. This is clear evidence that we need to improve our technology. We have spent a considerable amount of time analysing what in our procedures can be "gridified", and what is uniquely ours, in order that we can design our future evolution to make the best use of e-science tools.

Planning to make use of grid technologies will be a significant departure from previous activities at the BADC. Historically, the BADC was created just over six years ago, and was designed from scratch. Evolution since then has been my small incremental changes. It is our opinion that e-science will introduce a period of punctuated equilibrium – the BADC will oscillate between periods of relative stasis, where we will make small incremental changes, and periods of rapid change as new technologies are introduced. This leads to new challenges in organising our procedures and in terms of managing our archives so the users don't see any lack of service while new technologies are added to our structure.

Figure X: Schematic of the main components of BADC operations.

As much of this activity is essentially growing out of our core work package in middleware, we chose to advertise for our middleware person in the area of e-science. Although we advertised widely, in the end we appointed from within, and Kevin Marsh was appointed. From mid-November he will be taking responsibility for coordinating the system aspects of our e-science developments (again, regardless of direct e-science funding, these are things we need to do anyway). Our plan is to use some of our older systems to build e-science testbeds, coupled to limited test datasets. When we are satisfied that these add functionality, we will integrate them into our core activities. Early priorities in this area include:

- The use of the Storage Resource Broker (SRB) to manage our data across our own systems and the CLRC Atlas datastore. While we have reservations about the SRB technology as part of a wider area network (as seems to be envisaged by the national programme), we do think it will make managing our own data much easier.
- The implementation of the Live Access Server (LAS) for the Unified Model data we hold (both for the COAPEC programme and the generic NWP analyses).
- The implementation of suitable technology (there are still a number of candidates, including the LAS) to deliver a graphical interface to the ECMWF data.

The EU DataGrid project is a massive consortium with a mandate to produce a Grid designed to deliver petabytes of data from CERN to researchers world-wide. While most of the thrust of the work is based around the High Energy Physics community, one work package (WP9) is based around producing some demonstrator test-beds in the Earth Observation (EO) community. As these demonstrators are mainly atmospheric science EO activities, the BADC has joined in WP9 by providing user requirements and document critiques. While BADC involvement has been rather unsatisfactory from the point of view of our collaborators (who had hoped for us to do more, which we couldn't do for lack of funding), it has been very useful for us. If the NERC DataGrid is funded (see below), then we will take a more active role in EU DataGrid.

The BADC has had a high profile role in the preparation of full bids in response to the first round of the NERC call for proposals in e-science, with a major potential role in *e-climate* led by O'Neill at Reading, as well as a lesser potential role in *e-oceans*, led by Webb at Southampton. The BADC role in these proposals

would be to build *The NERC DataGrid*, in conjunction with colleagues in the CLRC e-science centre and in the US. Two other full-bid proposals (Allen's *climate-prediction.com* and Haine's *The Grid for Environmental Systems Diagnostics and Visualisation*) have indicated that their proposals would be strengthened by the existence of the NERC DataGrid. Because the NERC DataGrid concept has wider applicability than just e-climate, we have taken the unusual step of submitting the NERC DataGrid as a standalone¹ second-round outline bid, should e-climate be unsuccessful. We are also leading a second round bid in partnership with the DARC and the University of Aberystwyth, aiming to port the Met Office data assimilation suite and accompanying data to the wider UK community (PARADISE: Portable Assimilation of Remotely Accessible Data In Support of E-science). The key elements of the NERC DataGrid can be seen in Figure Y, full details can be found on the CAST website.

Figure Y: Schematic of the main query handling, processes and data flow required to provide a "NERC DataGrid". Query processing is depicted with thin lines, data transport by thick lines. The layers identify the planned inter-relationship of the various components. Note that components in shaded boxes should be available from other grid projects, although may not necessarily be available early in our project. One of the purposes of this diagram is to make clear that there is much integration and software development required to make use of these external developments in a NERC context

4.4.1 Climster

The BADC is involved in the EU bid Climate data storage and distribution as European infrastructure (CLIMSTER). The BADC will contribute both expertise and provide data within this pilot infrastructure project for the establishment of a distributed data archive network across Europe.

¹ Led by the BADC, with partners CLRC e-science centre and the British Oceanographic Data Centre.

5. CWP05: Programme support

(We used to call this chemistry support, but in reality, much of the work is supporting the wide variety of small programmes that do not provide significant supplementary funding).

5.1 ACSOE

Final release of ACSOE data took place in early July 2001. All the data are now public and accessible anonymously.

5.2 MST

The BADC were represented at the MST Radar experimenters meeting in May 2001, and advised on a number of data issues.

The BADC are also hosting the new MST radar website, and are involved with ongoing discussions with MST radar staff at RAL regarding data archiving, presentation, and the provision of complementary data. The new website can be found at <http://mst.nerc.ac.uk>.

5.3 Jet2000

This NERC funded project made observations over West Africa using the MRF C-130 aircraft. The Jet2000 archive is now populated. The BADC has VHS copies of the aircrafts video and is looking into purchasing equipment to allow VHS to MPEG conversion and thus allow FTP distribution of these products.

5.4 GOME

Due to a processing error, all the GOME data has been replaced.

5.5 NDSC

The BADC was presented at the NDSC Symposium celebrating its 10th birthday (cf. Section 5).

5.6 Chemistry Model output

Contacts with stratospheric modellers (F. Lefèvre & P. Simon, Météo-France; M. Chipperfield, Leeds) have been made at the NDSC Symposium in view of creating a database of stratospheric model results (from the ARPROBUS and SLIMCAT models) at BADC.

5.7 UARS Data from the UARS chemistry instruments:

HALOE-L2 data updates have stopped since March 2001 because the NASA LaRC Centerwide Network Firewall system was implemented around that time and HOPS was placed behind the firewall. Data will however soon be retrieved again from the HALOE webserver which is not protected by the firewall.

Also in July 2001, the BADC was informed that a final decision to shut off UARS instrument operations on September 30, 2001, has been made at NASA Headquarters. This will affect the HALOE data held at the BADC.

5.8 ESA Water Vapour

The European Space Agency funded a detailed study of the spectrum of water vapour to aid retrieval from GOME and SCIAMACHY. A small error in some of the data files stored at the BADC was reported in October 2000 and corrected immediately. This dataset

6. CWP06 Services and CAST

6.1 CAST

The integration of the CAST into the BADC has continued this year. The CAST home page has been simplified to allow users to go straight to the items of most relevance.

A collaborative workspace system called BSCW has been purchased and installed as part of CAST. This allows users to have discussions, share documents, contact other users and much more. Several themed workspaces have already been set up, including 'Solar variability and it's impact on climate change' and one for COAPEC users. A general workspace open to all BADC users has also been set up. All users registering with the BADC are now asked if they want to join the workspace system and other CAST initiatives, such as *Who's Who* (see below). The user account system for the BSCW system has been integrated with the BADC's so that the same username and password are used for both.

An institution search has been added which allows users to see which institutes are working on which of the datasets provided by the BADC.

A chat system based on a freeware package has been added to the BADC users workspace. As well as allowing users to have conversations they can upload and share image files (which could be a graph of experimental results, for example).

We are currently working on a *Who's Who* system which will allow users to search for other users based on different criteria. For example, users will be able to search for other users who have similar research interests, are using the same datasets or are at a particular institution. This will enable them to make contact and hopefully collaborate with each other. Since the BADC already has a large database of users we anticipate that this could be a very productive.

6.2 Highlighted Sites

New Highlighted Sites pages have been released on the following topics.

- Data centres
- International meteorological agencies
- National meteorological offices world-wide
- Spacecraft images

6.3 Trajectory service

The WWW trajectory model has continued to be popular. The table below shows the use in the past months.

Month	Number of users	Number of trajectories	Number of jobs
Jul	18	1984	441
Aug	12	59444	744
Sep	14	4166	186
Oct	14	1121	237
Nov	11	3298	169

6.4 Live Access Server

The Live Access Server has been installed at the BADC to allow users to visualize and subset data via their web browser. This will make it possible for users to examine data interactively at the BADC, without having to download large amounts of data. This system is in the process of being tested with data from the UM and COAPEC datasets.

6.5 Data formats

Documents describing to the Met Office PP format (used for UM and COAPEC data files) have been added to the BADC web site, along with software utilities to allow these data to be easily accessed. These also allow for the conversion of PP data into several other popular formats.

7. CWP07: Data Archaeology

7.1 SOUSY Radar Data

The BADC had a request from the user community regarding the availability of SOUSY radar data. The possibility of storing archive data from the SOUSY radar is current being investigated, and discussions have been held with the head of the SOUSY radar group, Dr J. Roettger, and the EISCAT group leader at RAL. This has also led to the likelihood of future SOUSY data being archived at BADC once EISCAT take over operation of the radar (2002).

7.2 Climate Data from Armagh Observatory

Discussions with staff at Armagh Observatory have led to an agreement that their long period climate data archive (1795-present) can be mirrored at the BADC as calibrated datasets become available. This is one of the longest datasets from a single site anywhere.

8. CWP08: Liaison and publicity

8.1 Liaison with other data centres or distributors

The BADC has been in contact with various data centres and their representatives.

- As part of a move to improve communication between data centres the BADC monthly meetings are now attended by representatives of the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC) also located at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.
- Sam Pepler attended the NERC Data Strategy Meeting
- Anne De Rudder is in regular contact with NERC data centres involved in URGENT (CEH & BGS): see WP11, URGENT.
- Discussions are underway with ETHER (IPSL atmospheric data centre, France) and Météo-France regarding the distribution of ERA-40. Additional contacts were made with the ETHER representatives at the NDSC Symposium.
- Locating atmospheric chemistry data in response to users queries has generated useful communication with NILU and NIWA.
- Discussions were held with representatives of various databases (NDSC, ENVISAT Cal/Val, European UV DB) at the NDSC Symposium.

8.2 Liaison with the academic community

- Posters and papers advertising for the BADC or for some of its specific resources were presented at international conferences (see Section 5).

- Liaison with British atmospheric scientists (science coordinators, principal investigators, graduate students) took place in the context of the data management associated to NERC thematic programmes (URGENT, Data Assimilation, CWVC) and core strategic activities (UWERN/UFAM, FAAM).
- BADC attendance at NERC programme launch meetings was ensured (Quantitative Precipitation Forecast).

8.3 Collaborative projects

ATMOS – The project proposal submitted to INTAS in October 2000 by BADC and its partners* has been selected for funding in the course of March. The co-operation agreement was signed at the end of August. The project official start date is September 1st, 2001 and its duration is 30 months. The project represents a modest total income of 10,000 Euros (about 6,300 GBP) for BADC, charges and overheads included, but it places BADC at the front line regarding collaboration with Eastern European countries. The project kick-off meeting will take place in Gumpoldskirchen (Austria) on November 16th.

8.4 Publicity Plans

As mentioned in the section 4.2 the BADC plans to revamp the website. In conjunction with this a new publicity leaflet will be produced along with flyers advertising particular datasets. The present plan is to produce a stockpile of publicity material from which event or location specific brochures, fliers and posters can be rapidly produced.

9. CWP09 Allied Research

Since the last steering committee meeting, Mr Sam Dean was appointed to the BADC research post for a one-year contract. Dr Martin Juckes has also joined the BADC, initially using his own funding as he holds a NERC Advanced Research Fellowship. He will take the BADC research position permanently once his existing funding is completed.

The main activities carried out under the auspices of the BADC research funding this year have revolved around the main thrust of Dean and Jucke's activities: Cloud Physics and Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange. Lawrence's main research activity has been a significant role in the design of the GRAPE (Global Retrieval of ATSR cloud Properties and Evaluation) proposal to the Clouds, Water Vapour and Climate (CWVC) thematic programme, although he also has played a significant role as a newly appointed honorary Principle Investigator within the Data Assimilation Research Centre (DARC). Other work has included leading the COAPEC² project: "The Maintenance and Decay of Predictability", as well as continuing supervision of his remote graduate students and further work with Dr Gray on the modelling of the QBO.

9.1 Cloud Physics

Mr Dean's work revolves around building a new parameterisation of orographic cirrus in the Unified Model (UM). This parameterisation is based around the influence of linear gravity waves produced by unresolved topography on grid box temperatures. The current state of the work is that the parameterisation has been

* Namely:

- Institute of Atmospheric Optics (IAO), Tomsk, Russia.
- Institute for Numerical Mathematics (INM), Moscow, Russia.
- Institute for Solar-Terrestrial Physics (ISTP), Irkutsk, Russia.
- Institute of Optical Monitoring (IOM), Tomsk, Russia.
- Geo-Information Centre (GIC), Tomsk, Russia.
- Environmental Software & Services GmbH, Gumpoldskirchen, Austria.

² Coupled Ocean Atmosphere Processes and European Climate

tested offline, has been installed in the UM, and model simulations are about to be carried out with the intention of comparing the model cirrus climatology with the ISCCP cloud data. As part of this comparison, Mr Dean will be looking into the details of the quality of the ISCCP cirrus, rather than relying uncritically on the data.

To this end, Mr Dean is in the process of obtaining the ISCCP D1 (3 hourly, global data from 1984-1999) and D2 (monthly mean data for 8 times of the day for 1984-1999) data in HDF format. The data obtained so far has been provided free of charge (by the Langley Data Centre), more recent data will be obtained, but we are not yet sure of the cost (as the ISCCP project will charge for the computer time to extract that data – expected to be of the order of a few thousand pounds). Dr .W. Rossow who is the PI of the ISCCP project has given us permission to put this data on the BADC, so that it can be made available to the wider UK community. We expect to link this data to the same middleware tools we will install to access the Unified Model and ECMWF data. Mr Dean will be producing the documentation over the next few months.

9.2 Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange

Martin Juckes is continuing his NERC Research Fellowship entitled "Wave dynamics and wave induced transport in the troposphere and lower stratosphere" and developing ideas on data assimilation.

Examination of the operational global analyses from the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) has revealed a surprising amount of upward motion in the winter polar vortex at lower stratospheric heights. This challenges existing assumptions about the way in which trace gases are transported around the stratosphere. In order to evaluate the reliability of the vertical motions obtained from the ECMWF data the analysis will be repeated on data obtained from the climate models.

See section 21 for publications in 2001.

9.3 Surface Processes Research

A model sensitivity study followed by a short presentation (cf. Section 5) was carried out by A. De Rudder in collaboration with P. Samuelson (University of Stockholm, Sweden) and J.-H. Lü (Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Beijing, China) at the Summer Colloquium on Land-Atmosphere Interactions and the Hydrological Cycle held in Trieste (Italy) in June.

10. CWP10 Maintenance of the NERC metadata gateway

The NERC metadata gateway software has been moved from its original location and installed on the BADC's Unix server. This is a more powerful machine and we now have better control of the system. The search forms have been updated and simplified.

Integration of other NERC sites into the system is planned for the current financial year.

11. WP10A: Metadata gateway

Lack of staff has delayed progress on this work package (that is, we have not been able to go out to data centres other than NEODC which was done last quarter). We have also had to wait until we had made progress on the core component of the problem (moving the gateway to the BADC server machine). A recruitment action for a BADC computer scientist is now complete and this person will perform the metadata tasks as well as other e-Science activities.

12. WP11: UTLS

UTLS data available from the BADC was presented at the 2nd National Conference of the Royal Meteorological Society. A presentation will also be made at the next UTLS workshop, "Transport and Chemistry", in December 2001.

A number of activities funded by UTLS have been reported in earlier sections.

12.1 Archived data

Data from the Egret campaign and the UWA lidar has been added to the archive. The only data needed to complete the EGRET archive are turbulence probe measurements. The UWA EGRET team will supply these data when they return from an experimental campaign in Australia in October 2001.

UTLS fourth round scoping study questionnaire has been sent out. Only a few responses have been received so far. Follow up and analysis of the scoping study will happen next quarter. The fourth round is concentrating on analysis of the data already collected, hence little data is expected to be archived from this round.

12.2 Auxiliary data

This is data requested via the scoping study. This data is likely to be useful to a larger user base than the UTLS community, and will continue after the UTLS has stopped as core.

Test data from the SLIMCAT model has been received and is currently being assessed. This data is likely to be of interest outside of the UTLS community as well.

Data from the Met Office Unified Model data is now being routinely extracted (see earlier). This data will be particularly useful for the UTLS community as the resolution of the mesoscale model is very high. Implementing and developing middleware tools should ensure users are able to use this data effectively.

The trajectory service developed for UTLS continues to be well used. The present BADC web trajectory service runs using the ECMWF operational analysis. Now that the BADC is archiving UM data regularly, a work-plan is being developed to incorporate this archive with the trajectory service. The integration of the mesoscale model data would be particularly useful, as this would give much more accurate trajectories to compare to the UTLS campaign data.

13. WP12 URGENT

The BADC has set up the URGENT Data Management and Quality Assurance (DMQA) WWW pages providing documents and templates related to URGENT data management. This site is accessible from both the URGENT site at NERC and the URGENT Web page at BADC.

The current status of the URGENT air projects is summarised in Table 1. Among the 8 projects delivering non-confidential observation data, five have formally come to an end recently. Data management plans have been obtained from all projects but four. The archive has continued to be populated and updated, but only by groups belonging to the two projects that had already started to do so last January. In order to match new data arrivals, the documentation archive has undergone substantial revision. A summary of GST/02/1971 conclusions has been provided to BADC as an ArcView CDROM. Since the BADC would need to acquire

the corresponding (commercial) software, the CD will probably be made available through CEH Monkswood.

URGENT air projects current status.

GST /02//	PI	Deliverable	Finished	DMP	Data in archive
1971	Thornes	Confidential data	Yes	Yes	/
1974	Simmonds	Experimental/observation data	Yes	Yes	
1981	Harrison	Experimental/observation data	Yes	Yes	Yes
1983	Smith	Experimental/observation data	Yes	Yes	
1996	Ingham	Software	Yes		/
2090	Hancock	Feasibility study	Yes		/
2222	Richards	Experimental/observation data	Yes	Yes	Soon
2225	Gallagher	Experimental/observation data		Yes	Yes
2229	Tomlin	Model		Yes	/
2231	Belcher	Experimental/observation data		Yes	Soon
2244	Fowler	Experimental/observation data	Yes	Yes	
2254	Clarke	Model	Yes		/
2602	Baker	Experimental/observation data			

A number of meetings with principal investigators and/or members of their staff have taken place in order to provide support in DMP writing and data formatting and submission (GST/02/1974, 2222, 2244). A large amount of reminders and/or support has also been provided by e-mail and telephone to participants to all projects. Data from GST/02/2222 and 2231 are currently being formatted with BADC's help and should be submitted soon. The data manager of GST/02/1974 has left Bristol University, leaving the work unfinished. A reminder has been addressed by NERC to Drs Ingham (GST/02/1996 – no DMP nor metadata submitted) and Smith (GST/02/1983 – no data submitted although the project is finished).

Co-ordinated action with the other three data centres (BGS, CEH Wallingford, CEH Monkswood) has continued to take place through the meetings of the Data Management and Quality Assurance (DMQA) committee. The four data centres (DC) have held meetings devoted to the data dissemination issue, for which special funding has been requested. PC-based prototypes of a metadata capture tool and elements of a metadata gateway have been developed at CEH Wallingford and tested by all 4 DC. The BADC has taken part to this endeavour and provided its contribution to the underlying thesaurus. This task is expected to continue for one year.

Posters on the URGENT programme and more especially the URGENT air archive have been presented at the Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality in March and at the URGENT annual meeting in April (see Section 6).

14. WP13 COAPEC

The 100-year COAPEC dataset from the control run of the Hadley Centre's HadCM3 climate model has been extracted from the Met Office. The archive has been established at the BADC, along with associated web pages and documentation. The extraction of a complementary 1000-year dataset of limited parameters is currently underway. An associated CAST workspace has been set up for COAPEC researchers, which is expected to prove very useful for researchers involved in exchanging information and ideas.

15. WP14 Data Assimilation Research Centre

The BADC is not as yet funded to participate in the DARC project. However it is obvious that there is a great deal of mutual benefit if the BADC is involved. At present a BADC staff member is visiting the University of Reading one day per week to work with UGAMP staff on ECMWF issues. These visits also allow the BADC to get involved with providing data support to the Data Assimilation Research Centre (DARC). The BADC presented a poster at the DARC opening ceremony in June and has contacted PIs to assess their data requirements. It is already apparent that the large data sets produced by the Envisat satellite need to be considered in the BADC's storage plans.

The objective of one of the DARC's projects is to set-up a demonstration portable data assimilation system outside of the Met Office computing systems. Regular meetings are held with DARC personnel at the University of Reading to work on this issue. A research proposal is being written to extend the scope of this project to run distributed data assimilation within an e-Science context. The BADC will be part of this project. Initial steps have been made to establish a formal agreement with the Met Office to allow the porting of their database and data assimilation software.

16. WP15 Data Assimilation

16.1 Cambridge Atmospheric Chemical Data

This dataset was part of the 'Assimilation of Remote-sensed Data for Application in the Atmospheric and Oceanographic Sciences' (ARDAAOS) thematic programme. The dataset has now been retrieved from David Lary at Cambridge and stored at the BADC. It is planned that a dedicated server will be set up to distribute these data in the manner originally used by D. Lary.

16.2 ENVISAT

The BADC has successfully negotiated an agreement for the University of Oxford to download data using the RAL ATSR groups DDS receiver. This involved close liaison with ESA, RAL and University of Oxford staff.

17. WP17 CWVC

An enquiry addressed to the project principal investigators and some of their collaborators, completed by discussions with Keith Bower, science co-ordinator of the programme, led to the writing of a data management proposal submitted to the programme steering committee. Since some PIs have only partially answered the enquiry, or have not answered it at all yet, collection of information is still going on. Over the twelve projects funded in rounds 1 and 2, three have not answered (2318, Harries; 2324 & 2881, Whiteway) and two have provided very incomplete information (2316 & 2874, Choularton). Four of these five projects are expected to deliver a substantial amount of data. This information is required to get a global picture of the participants' needs and to assess the BADC resources involved.

A CWVC Web front page has been created (<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/data/cwvc/>). It includes links to the CWVC documentation at NERC and will be a gateway to the future CWVC data archive.

18. WP18 UWERN / UFAM / FAAM.

As a preparation to the UWERN data management plan, discussions with Alan Blyth, UFAM science co-ordinator, led to a common e-mail to UFAM heads of group. It will be followed by an enquiry with UWERN groups after the BADC steering committee will have clarified BADC's role within NERC core strategic

activities. Contacts have been made with Charles Kilburn regarding the Chilbolton radar data sets of potential interest to UWERN.

18.1 FAAM

BADC staff attended the UFAM Town meeting in Manchester (February 2001) discuss data issues with a number of researchers.

The BADC organised a meeting (October 2001) at RAL to discuss data storage and format issues for data which will be produced when the new aircraft becomes operational (July 2002). It appears likely that the majority of the recommendations made by the BADC to the meeting will be implemented, and that the BADC will be the archive of choice for FAAM data.

18.2 Meteosat Second Generation

Keith Browning suggested that the UWERN community would use MSG data extensively. The BADC has investigated the likely impact and data handling requirements on the BADC. The data storage requirement is modest, but it may have some resource impact if the data is required in near-real time for data assimilation.

19. Usage statistics

19.1 Usage by data set

The table below shows the number of registered users of the various data sets as of the end of October 2001, the approximate size of the data sets and the number and size of the data transfers for the year November 2000 to October 2001. * in the users column indicates public access data sets.

Dataset	users	Size (MB)	Files Transferred	Data Transferred (MB)
CDs	*	14721	47273	6,596
acsoe	*	3550	2648	419
cira	*	2	653	43
clael3	*	10903	31563	7,810
coapec	16	129661	1397	21,638
ecmwf-e40	Not Released	50834	64	1
ecmwf-era	320	457216	166256	252,431
ecmwf-op	364	228742	90479	151,160
ecmwf-trj	274	27193	1030	1,377
esa-wv	*	5	345	236
export	19	238	2097	1,452
firetracc	No Data Yet	0	62	0
gome	47	1567	3502	822
haloel2	58	29067	312	8,495
haloel3	*	537	3418	91
hyrex	15	8777	385	31
isamsl2	30	1810	67	1
isamsl3	*	1866	341	43
jet2000	12	1159	1421	4,272
llims	*	918	3197	946
meteosat	*	7697	1929	302
misl3	14/*	5183	41856	8,186
mst	19	144850	61516	30,578
sams	*	891	1042	631
soapex	22	14	267	83
toms	*	1846	18308	3,247
ugamp-o3	*	83	175	342
ukmo-aam	*	5	554	22
ukmo-assim	201	19904	31036	102,340
ukmo-clim	428	3120	1801	729
gosta/gosta CD	176/92	1277	2773	7,659
ukmo-mrf	19	4889	119	1
ukmo-rad	401	35839	1335002	48,023
ukmo-surface	852	30546	382316	33,176
ukmo-synop	407	3625	1678	565
ukmo-tovs	133	1136	88	878
ukmo-um	15	433671	75	39
urgent	31	46	1654	255
utils	30	1316	1003	731
virtem	*	257	43	0

19.2 Registered users

A registered user is someone who has registered their details with the BADC *and* registered for at least one dataset. The growth in the BADC user base continues. Non-atmospheric disciplines also continue to rise faster than atmospheric science use. The tables below show the current breakdown of users by region, institute type and Discipline.

Total registered users	1686
Number of users active in any calendar month	~240
Number of users active in 2001 so far	882

Region	Users
UK	76%
Europe	13%
USA and Canada	6%
Other	6%

Institute Type	Users
Government	13%
NERC	6%
Other	5%
University	76%

Discipline	Users
Atmospheric	43%
TFW	9%
Marine	7%
Earth Sci/Obs	17%
Other	25%

20. Resources

20.1 Finance

The BADC funding will be discussed at a meeting that will decide on the funding of UCAS. This will take place on the Friday before the steering committee meets. Dr Thorpe will attend the BADC steering meeting and it should be possible to discuss the future funding situation.

Actual spend for financial year 2000/01

Income	£k
Receipts	572
Expenditure	
Recurrent	178
Capital	59
Staff	320
Total	557
Balance	
	15

20.2 Staff

The current structure is depicted in the following organogram. There are three main areas involved in the running of the archive, plus the research work. These are all overseen by the BADC head – Bryan Lawrence.

The BADC staff allocation as of November 2001 is as follows:

Staff Member	Title and responsibility	Time allocation
Dr Bryan Lawrence	Head	50% Management 50% Research
Dr Sam Pepler	Project Scientist, responsible for operation integrity of BADC.	100% Operations
Dr Anne De Rudder	Science Programme Manager, responsible for Programme support e.g. URGENT, UTLS	100% Programmes
Mr Andrew Harwood	Infrastructure Manager, responsible for the development and implementation of technical developments.	100% Infrastructure

Ms Anabelle Menochet	Data Scientist, responsible for user support and UKMO data acquisition.	100% Operations
Mr Ag Stephens	Data Scientist, DARC and ECMWF	60% Operations 40% Programmes
Dr Kevin Marsh	Data Scientist, responsible for UTLS programme. Moving to middleware activities. UTLS responsibilities will be reallocated to Anne De Rudder.	60% Programmes 30% Operations 10% Infrastructure
Mr Chris Harrold	CAST Programmer	100% Infrastructure
Mr Richard Stamper	Metadata	80% Infrastructure (starts in December)
Dr Martin Jukes	Research Scientist supported by NERC fellowship.	100% Research (from July)
Mr Sam Dean	Research Scientist	100% Research (from July) [1 year contract]
Peter Chiu / Chris Robey / Brian Coan /Matthew Wild	System Management	90% Infrastructure

20.3 Hardware

A schematic of the BADC hardware based at RAL is shown below:

It shows the following major components:

- **Tornado:** Compaq ES40, Quad alpha 500, 2GB memory, 3 internal disk racks filled with 18GB disks. Dat drive, Exabyte drive, CDROM.
- **Cirrus:** Sun Ultra60, 300MHz, 256MB memory, Dat drive, CDROM.

- **Tornado:** Compaq ES40, Quad alpha 500, 2GB memory, 3 internal disk racks filled with 18GB disks. Dat drive, Exabyte drive, CDROM.
- **Cirrus:** Sun Ultra60, 300MHz, 256MB memory, Dat drive, CDROM.
- **Disk Box:** 6 x 18GB disk, UltraSCSI
- **RAID Array:** 2 Transtec RAID arrays, each 14 x 50GB disks (600 GB User space: total of 1.2TB), UltraSCSI, dual controller
- **Tape Library:** Qualstar TLS46120 tape library, contains 3AIT-2 drives, 120 slots
- **Switch:** 3COM 100baseT switch
- **Gb Switch:** Fibre 1000base switch
- **Other:** Staff PCs and AMD Workstations.

New Components on order:

- **RAID Array** disk storage connected by Fibre channel.
- **Tape Library:** Qualstar TLS41230 tape library, contains 4AIT-3 drives, 300 slots

Additionally the BADC has a HP workstation within the Met Office with an AIT-2 tape drive. This is used to transfer UM and other bulky Met Office data sets to the BADC via the postal service.

21. Publications, communications, reports

- A. De Rudder, *The Urban Air Quality Archive of the British Atmospheric Data Centre*, Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality, Loutraki, Greece, 19-23 March 2001. — Poster + paper.
- A. De Rudder, L. Gray, A. Harwood, J. Kettleborough, B. Lawrence, K. Marsh, A. Ménochet and S. Pepler, *Middle Atmosphere Resources from the British Atmospheric Data Centre*, XXVIth General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society, Nice, France, 25-30 March 2001. — Poster.
- A. De Rudder, *The URGENT Air Archive at BADC*, URGENT Annual Meeting, Birmingham, 5-6 April 2001. — Poster.
- De Rudder, P. Samuelson and J.-H. Lü, *On the sensitivity of BATS to heterogeneity in precipitation distribution*, Summer colloquium on Land-Atmosphere Interactions and the Hydrological Cycle, Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste, Italy, May 28 - June 14, 2001. — Talk.
- A. De Rudder and B. Lawrence, *The British Atmospheric Data Centre: its scientific resources and its role in the 'ATMOS' project*, International Conference on Modeling, Databases and Information Systems for Atmospheric Sciences "MODAS – 2001", Irkutsk, 25-29 June 2001. — Invited talk.
- A. De Rudder and S. Williams, BADC resources of interest for NDSC research, NDSC 2001 Symposium "Celebrating 10 Years of Atmospheric Research", Arcachon, France, 24-27 September 2001. — Poster.
- Lawrence, B.N., A Gravity Wave Induced Quasi-Biennial Oscillation in a three-dimensional mechanistic model. *Q. J. Roy. Met. Soc.*, 127, 2005-2021. (2001)
- Gray, L J. E.F. Drysdale, B.N. Lawrence and T.J. Dunkerton. On the inter annual variability of the Northern Hemisphere circulation: the role of the quasi biennial oscillation. *Q. J. Roy. Met. Soc.*, 127,1413-1432 (2001)
- Osprey, S.M., B.N. Lawrence. A possible mechanism for in situ forcing of planetary waves in the summer extratropical mesosphere, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, ,28 , 1183-1186 (2001)

IN CONFIDENCE

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 5. Verbal feedback on the NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science.

The Committee is asked to address and discuss issues related to NCAS, in particular regarding the role of BADC in data management of NERC core strategic activities.

IN CONFIDENCE

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 6. NERC Metadata Gateway.

The NERC Metadata Gateway has been updated and simplified. The next step is to connect all NERC data centres to it. Metadata gateway issues will be discussed verbally.

IN CONFIDENCE

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 7. Budget.

If possible, a document outlining the BADC budget (as part of NCAS) will be provided. In any case, a verbal report of the status of BADC funding within NCAS will be supplied. (The NCAS budget is to be discussed at a meeting on the 23rd of November).